

Literature reveals that no similar work on these proteins has been reported.

Experimental

The beans were purchased from the local market (1983 harvest). Reagents used were of A.R. grade. Colorimetric measurements were made by a ECIL GS66B spectrophotometer and uv spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss Specord UV-VIS apparatus.

The proteins from the three beans were isolated, purified and homogeneity was ascertained by PAGE⁹ and as reported in our earlier work^{5,10}. The electrophoresis⁹ was carried out in the pH range 3–9 using acetate, tris-glycine and tris-borate buffers under varying voltage of 400–500 V and time 3–6 h. The protein content was determined spectrophotometrically¹¹ and molecular weights were determined by gel filtrations¹². The proteins were subjected to Manual-Edman degradation^{13–16} by dissolving each protein (200 nmol) in aqueous dioxane (50%, 6 ml) and treating with phenyl isothiocyanate (0.1 ml) at the pH 9. The solution was stirred for 1.5 h at 40°, extracted several times with benzene and concentrated to dryness in vacuum over NaOH. The sodium salt was redissolved in water and acidified with 6N HCl. The PTH-amino acid was extracted with ethyl acetate, and the residue recovered by concentrating the aqueous solution was submitted to the same cycle of operations. Thus, seven sequential residues for each protein were separated. PTH-amino acids were identified by tlc¹⁷ and uv¹⁸. Tlc was carried¹⁷ out on silica plates (0.5 mm × 20 × 20 cm) using hexane-n-butanol (3 : 2, v/v) and benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1, v/v) as the developing solvents and the spots were located in iodine chamber. Uv spectra were recorded in ethanol (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) and molar extinction coefficients calculated¹⁹ at 245 and 269 nm. The ratio $\epsilon_{245}/\epsilon_{269}$ was calculated and served as a sensitive criterion for the purity of products¹⁹. The R_f values and $\epsilon_{245}/\epsilon_{269}$ of the unknown PTH-amino acids were in good agreement with those of the standard PTH-amino acids prepared²⁰ for this purpose.

The globulin 100 fraction was the primary source of the major bean protein and accounts for about 40% of the total. The molecular weight was found to be about 1,86,000. Partial amino acid sequence of the globulins as determined by Edman method are as follows: *P. vulgaris*, Arg-Val-Phe-Lys-Gly-Ala-Met-; *V. mungo*, Phe-Glu-Lys-Val-Pro-Arg-Leu-; *V. radiata*, Gly-Val-Val-Cys-Lys-Leu-Ile-. The readily accessible amino-terminal sequences of proteins have been of interest in several fields. The study of the amino-terminal sequences of nascent polypeptide has demonstrated that many proteins excreted from cells are synthesised as precursors. Further, amino-terminal partial sequences can be correlated with nucleotide sequences determined from cloned cDNA or genomic DNA.

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Copper with Bromopyrogallol Red and Benzyldimethylphenylammonium Chloride

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BROMOPYROGALLOL red in presence of long-chain quaternary ammonium salts, viz. cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide, benzyldimethyltetradecylammonium chloride and tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide has been in use in the spectrophotometric determination of some metal ions¹⁻⁶. In this paper, we present a method for extractive spectrophotometric determination of copper in micro quantities using bromopyrogallol red (BPR) and benzyldimethylphenylammonium chloride (BDPA-

chloride). Preparation and some applications of BDPA-chloride were found reported⁷⁻¹¹.

Experimental

A Hilger—Uvispek photoelectric spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used.

The standard stock solution of copper (500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared from $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR). Solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. A 0.05 M solution of BDPA-chloride in water and a 0.05% solution of BPR in ethanol (1 : 1) were employed as the reagents. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade salts.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the test solution containing 4.0–50 μg of copper(II), KH_2PO_4 –NaOH buffer (2 ml), the BPR solution (1 ml) and the BDPA-chloride solution (1 ml) were added. The pH of the aqueous phase (5 ml) was maintained at 7 ± 0.5 . After adding isobutanol (10 ml) to it, the resulting mixture was shaken for a few seconds and the organic layer separated. Absorbance of the extract was measured at 625 nm against the reagent blank. Copper content in unknown solutions was computed from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Copper(II) reacts with bromopyrogallol red (BPR) in presence of the quaternary ammonium salt BDPA-chloride to form ion-association complex which is completely extractable into isobutanol. The extract shows maximum absorption at 625 nm. Beer's law is obeyed for 0.4–5 ppm of copper, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity being $1.286 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0049 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The colour of the extracted species was found stable for more than 48 h. The results of extraction studies show that copper can be quantitatively extracted in isobutanol from an aqueous solution containing BPR and BDPA-chloride at pH 5.5–9.0. Below and above this pH range, the extraction of copper decreases. The extracted species exhibited constant and maximum absorption when the pH of the aqueous phase was maintained within the range 5.5–9.0. Buffer solutions constituting HCl and KCl, sodium acetate and acetic acid, KH_2PO_4 and NaOH, and H_3BO_3 , KCl and NaOH, were employed during the investigations.

The effect of BPR concentration on the absorbance was studied. It was found that 1 ml of a 0.05% solution of BPR was adequate for complete extraction of the complex. Use of a solution of concentration below 0.04% resulted in low absorbance while a BPR solution having concentration beyond 0.1% produced considerable difficulty in measuring the colour intensity. As regards BDPA-chloride, the lower limit of concentration was 0.006 M with respect to the aqueous layer. Below

this concentration, the absorbance of the extract was found to be low. Increased concentration, however, did not produce any significant change in the colour intensity.

The composition of the copper-BPR complex ion was determined by Job's method of continuous variation¹² and the mole-ratio method¹³. The results indicate the composition as 1 : 2 (Cu—BPR).

Effect of diverse ions : A number of representative ions were examined for their interference in the determination of copper by the recommended procedure. The tolerance limit was set at the amount required to cause less than 2% error in the recovery of copper. It was found that Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ag^I , Au^{III} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Sn^{II} , Pb^{II} , As^{III} , As^V , Sb^{III} , V^V , Cr^{VI} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Co^{II} , Rh^{III} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , fluoride, bromide, iodide, thiosulphate, oxalate, citrate, tartarate, thiourea, cyanide and thiocyanate did not interfere when present in more than equal amounts with Cu (20 μg). Equal amounts of Cd^{II} , Bi^{III} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} and Ni^{II} interfered seriously. Tolerance limit of some metal ions (having serious interference) could be improved by making use of masking agents.

Applications : Copper was determined from the following standard samples. Dissolution of the materials to obtain the final solution for its use in the determination of copper by the proposed method was done following the standard procedure. The results as obtained from three determinations of each sample are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN ALLOYS

Samples with No. and (composition, %)	Cu found (%)
Gun metal (6 g) (Cu, 86.4, Zn, 1.30, Sn, 10.5, Pb, 1.02, Fe, 0.02, P, 0.11, Ni 0.26)	86.02 85.96 85.82
Aluminium alloy (20 b) (Cu, 4.10; Fe, 0.43, Mn, 0.19, Ni, 1.99, Si, 0.29, Mg, 1.61)	4.135 4.138 4.136
Cupronickel alloy (19 a) (Cu, 67; Fe, 0.88, Mn, 0.80, Ni, 81.2)	66.952 66.29 66.99

(The samples were obtained from B.A.S. Ltd., England.)

A comparative study (Table 2) shows that the present method has comparable sensitivity with the most of the extensively used colorimetric methods

TABLE 2—COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SOME COLORIMETRIC METHODS FOR COPPER USING DIFFERENT REAGENTS

Reagents	λ_{max} nm	Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$
Dithizone ^a	583	2.89×10^4	0.002 2
Diethyldithiocarbamate ^a	486	1.59×10^4	0.004 0
2,2-Biquinoline ^a	546	6.35×10^3	0.01
2,9-Dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline ^a	457	7.8×10^3	0.008
Present work	625	1.296×10^4	0.004 9

^aRef 14.

for determination of copper. Though less sensitive, the present method is much more selective than dithizone method. Moreover, the present method is very simple and rapid, providing good recovery of copper in presence of most of the common ions. The results are accurate within $\pm 2\%$, rendering the proposed method fairly precise and reproducible. The total operation for each run requires only 10–15 min.

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Estimation of Ethambutal in Pharmaceutical Preparations using some Inorganic Oxidants

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(+)-2,2'-(Ethylenedimino)di-1-butanol dihydrochloride is an orally effective chemotherapeutic agent specially active against the genus mycobacterium including *M. tuberculosis*. In the present work, (+)-2,2'-(ethylenedimino)di-1-butanol dihydrochloride is determined in its various pharmaceutical preparations, viz. using some inorganic oxidants like Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} or V^{V} . The method is highly useful for determining the active ingredient of drug samples accurately without using any complicated procedure and sophisticated instruments. This method is operable at micro sample size, quick and accurate (within $\pm 1\%$ error) as compared to the B.P. method^{1,1}. Results obtained with the present method are compared with the standard method (Table 3).

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) and ammonium metavanadate(V) solutions were prepared in $36 \times 10^{-1} M H_2SO_4$ medium. Potassium hexacyanoferrate solution was standardised iodometrically, and ammonium hexanitratocerate and ammonium metavanadate solutions were standardised by ferrous sulphate or Mohr's salt reagent. All reagents used were of A.R. (B.D.H.) grade. Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) solution could not be prepared in large amount because solution decomposed fairly rapidly. Zinc sulphate was used as catalyst for quantitative oxidation of ethambutol with Fe^{III} in acidic media. Ce^{IV} and V^{V} solutions were stable for several days in acidic medium.

In the preliminary experiments, a known amount of (+)-2,2'-(ethylenedimino)di-1-butanol hydrochloride prepared in distilled water was added to a 10 ml of different molar concentration of Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} or V^{V} reagent in volumetric flask at room temperature (25°). The contents were allowed to react at different intervals of time with occasional shaking. The excess of Fe^{III} was determined with $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ sodium thiosulphate using 10% potassium iodide (5 ml) and starch as an indicator. Excess of Ce^{IV} was determined by $25 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as an indicator and excess of V^{V} was determined by $25 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferrous ammonium sulphate using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator (colour rapidly changed from red to green).

Quantitative oxidations of the butanol hydrochloride were not reproducible and non-stoichiometric in various media other than sulphuric acid medium. It is evident from Table 1 that the

TABLE 1—EXTENT OF OXIDATION OF THE BUTANOL HYDROCHLORIDE SAMPLE IN DIFFERENT MOLAR CONCENTRATION OF OXIDANT

	Reagent concentration (M)		
	1×10^{-1}	8×10^{-1}	5×10^{-1}
Fe^{III}			
Time (min)			
10	94.66	95.86	96.22
15	96.42	97.28	98.66
20	97.86	98.22	99.99
25	97.96	98.46	100.21
30	98.22	101.11	104.22
Ce^{IV}			
Time (min)			
10	99.02	101.11	104.22
15	100.12	101.68	101.88
20	100.22	101.72	104.92
25	100.26	100.76	104.94
30	100.28	100.78	104.94
V^{V}			
Time (min)			
10	95.28	96.22	97.82
15	96.98	98.26	101.22
20	97.62	99.01	101.22
25	98.96	100.02	101.86
30	98.98	100.02	101.38